

A Comprehensive Review on Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD): Clinical Advancement and Drug Treatments

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ABSTRACT

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Hepatic steatosis, fibrosis, cirrhosis, and even hepatocellular cancer can all be part of NAFLD, which also includes less severe forms of fatty liver disease. The global epidemic of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease is mostly attributable to the accumulation of triglycerides and free fatty acids in the liver, a condition exacerbated by obesity and insulin resistance (NAFLD). Metabolic abnormalities or insulin resistance at the disease's physiological core are just two of the many factors that have been hypothesised to have a role in NAFLD development. The risk of death from both liver disease and cardiovascular disease is increased in patients with NAFLD, and NAFLD is quickly becoming the most common reason for a liver transplant, surpassing even liver cancer. Although a liver biopsy is still the gold standard for diagnosis, advances in noninvasive imaging, biochemical, and genetic tests promise to give future clinicians a wealth of new data with which to better understand the disease's pathophysiology and devise more precise treatments. There are already a number of drugs and supplements used for the treatment of NAFLD, but none of them have proven to be the "magic bullet" needed to stop this alarming trend. This review aims to summarise what is currently known regarding the epidemiology, risk factors, diagnosis, pathophysiology, pathologic changes, natural history, and treatment of NAFLD to aid in better understanding the illness and better managing patients with NAFLD.

Graphical Abstract:

1. Introduction

Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is on the rise as one of the leading causes of liver illness[1]. The annual cost of treating NAFLD is expected to be over £35 billion in four European nations and over \$100 billion in the United States (the United Kingdom, France, Germany, and Italy). NAFLD describes a group of liver illnesses that can arise from factors other than excessive alcohol consumption[2]. Recently, NAFLD was called metabolic-associated fatty liver disease to reflect the fact that it is a metabolic disorder (MAFLD). By designating it as "Mad Cow" instead of "non-alcohol-related liver disease," the medical community acknowledges that "MAFLD" is a distinct disease entity [3]. For the sake of clarity, I shall refer to NAFLD throughout this review. Hepatic steatosis that affects more than 5% of the liver is included in NAFLD[4].

In some cases, people with NAFLD (which includes steatosis, inflammation, and cellular damage) develop nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)[5]. Among the primary causes of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and the need for a liver transplant, NAFLD is frequently cited[6]. The illness is associated with a wide range of extrahepatic diseases, including cardiovascular complications. About a quarter of the population has NAFLD, making it another epidemic along with obesity[7]. There is a connection between NAFLD and obesity and type 2 diabetes (T2D). More than 90% of extremely obese people and 70% of those who are simply overweight suffer from this disease[8]. Patients with MASH who develop hepatic fibrosis have a much higher risk of dying. NAFL and NASH are not limited to obese people of any ethnicity[9]. Accumulation of fat is a potential problem among the Asian population at[10].

Inflammation in the lobes and ballooning to a greater extent are linked to lower body mass in Asians than in non-Asians[11]. It appears that there is a significant racial disparity in the prevalence of NAFLD. In terms of race,

Hispanics have the highest prevalence of NAFL and NASH, followed by Blacks and Whites and Asians in descending order of prevalence[12]. Prevalence of NAFLD is also on the rise in children and teenagers. NAFLD cannot be treated with any currently available pharmaceuticals[13]. The lack of reliable non-invasive biomarkers[14] may be the result of the fact that NAFLD is a complex disease. This review looks at the pathophysiology of NAFLD, the existing diagnostic methods, and sirtuins as a potential disease-causing SIRT[15].

2. Epidemiology

In terms of symptoms and prognosis, NAFLD is a complex disease[16]. Cardiovascular disease, extrahepatic malignancies, and liver-related complications are the leading causes of death in patients with NAFLD, however the exact order varies throughout prospective studies of this population[17]. Three landmark studies from the field of epidemiology were published in 2008, establishing the association between NAFLD and CKD risk (Figure 1). In a cross-sectional study of 2103 Italian outpatients with T2D, It has reported that NAFLD (as detected by ultrasonography) was associated with an approximately 1.9-fold increase in the risk of CKD stage ₃ defined as an eGFR ₆₀ mL/min/1.73 m² with or without coexisting overt proteinuria. This was the case regardless of age, sex, smoking, a history.

Figure 1 Structure of liver lobule

3. Pathophysiology of NAFLD

The exact mechanisms at play in the onset of NASH are not well known. There has been a lot of research on the pathophysiology of NAFLD and NAS in animals recently, with a lot of attention paid to the many dietary models that have been used (high fructose, high fat, or methionine/choline deficient diet) (MCD). This data supports the idea that there are two stages in the progression of NASH. Many factors contribute to insulin resistance. Both the metabolic syndrome and NASH are characterised by an increase in fat accumulation and adipocyte differentiation, both of which contribute to insulin resistance. NAFLD can be split into two categories. The first type of NAFLD has only a limited relationship to metabolic syndrome, and insulin resistance is commonly believed to be the fundamental pathophysiological mechanism behind it. Second, there is a subtype of NAFLD associated with viral infections that can lead to hepatic steatosis. Infections like hepatitis C and HIV are just one possible cause; other factors include toxins (such as lipodystrophy, cachexia, or intestinal bypass surgery) and drugs (such as glucocorticoids, tamoxifen, tetracycline, amiodarone, methotrexate, valproic acid, vinyl chloride).

4. Diagnosis

Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is diagnosed by ruling out other potential causes of steatosis (such as alcohol and steatogenic medications), subsequently determining the likelihood that the patient would progress to end-stage fibrosis and nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH).¹⁰ However, the usual technique of only investigating in the presence of elevated liver transaminases is limited in its efficacy because many patients with NAFLD have normal liver function tests.¹⁵ Transaminase levels should also be evaluated in patients at high risk for the illness, such as those with type 2 diabetes or metabolic syndrome.

5. Fibrosis

The presence or absence of significant fibrosis is the key prognostic hallmark in NAFLD, making risk stratification of all patients with NAFLD essential.^{5,6} The severity of fibrosis can be measured with a number of different serological assays (such as the NAFLD Fibrosis Score [NFS], BARD, and FIB-4), as well as more expensive commercial testing (such as the FibroScan). Simple internet tools can be used to determine the biochemical and clinical parameters used in these tests, so

they do not cost anything above what is already spent on normal haematology and biochemistry examinations (eg Enhanced Liver Fibrosis Score [ELF test], Fibrotest, FibroMeter NAFLD). The tests often have two different cutoffs, one for detecting and ruling out severe fibrosis and another for detecting and ruling out mild fibrosis.

6. Steatosis

Ultrasound has long been the go-to diagnostic tool for diagnosing steatosis due to its low cost and ease of availability. However, its sensitivity is low, only being able to identify steatosis at a 20% level. There are other validated serological indicators, such as the Fatty Liver Index (FLI), the Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Disease Fat Score (NAFLD FS), and the Hepatic Steatosis Index (HIS), with AUROC values of 0.83, 0.80, and 0.81, respectively.^{17, 18} Because they just require the entry of basic clinical data into free online algorithms, these tests could be especially helpful in contexts where imaging is too expensive or otherwise inaccessible (Table 1).

7. Management

7.1 Cardiovascular risk factor modification

Management of NAFLD centres on ensuring that the patient's blood pressure, cholesterol levels, body mass index, smoking habits, and glucose levels are all under control. This will mostly take place in primary care, however it may be integrated into multidisciplinary specialist clinics.

7.2 Diet and exercise

Patients with NASH who lose at least 5% of their body weight experience histological resolution of the illness, and approximately half of patients who lose 10% of their body weight experience regression of fibrosis.²⁴ Yet, even in a trial setting, only 10% of patients lost 10% of their initial weight with lifestyle adjustments.²⁴ Patients should be provided with a nutritional assessment and referred to local weight loss support groups.

7.3 Pharmacotherapies

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Table 1. Emerging drugs for non-alcoholic steatohepatitis in phase III trials

Mechanism of action	Drug	Primary Endpoint	Clinical trial	Expected Completion date
PPAR/Agonist	Elafibranor	Resolution of NASH without worsening of fibrosis	RESOLUTION	December 2021
ASK1 inhibitor	Selonserebit	>1 stage improvement in fibrosis.	STELLAR4	January 2020
FXR agonist	Obeticholic acid	Fibrosis improvement composite endpoint; improvement in >1 stage of fibrosis NASH resolution with no worsening of fibrosis	REGENERATE	October 2021
CCR2/5	Cenicriviroc	Improvement in >1 stage of fibrosis and no worsening of NASH	AURORA	July 2019

8. Cirrhosis

Appropriate screening for HCC, oesophageal varices, and other cirrhosis sequelae is necessary for patients with NASH cirrhosis. Early evaluation by a transplant centre is warranted in cases of ascites, variceal haemorrhage, or hepatic encephalopathy, all of which indicate decompensation.

9. Liver cells and NAFLD

Lipid intake, production, oxidation, and transport to peripheral tissues all occur in the liver, making it a key organ in lipid metabolism. Hepatocytes, the parenchymal cells that make up most of the liver's cellular population, are just one type of liver cell. Hepatic NK cells, hepatic stellate cells, Kupffer cells, and liver sinusoidal endothelial cells (LSECs) are all non-parenchymal cells found in the liver. Despite hepatocytes' prominence in hepatic processes like lipid metabolism, KCs are also crucial in this organ's inflammatory response. About 30% of sinusoidal cells are KCs, and they make up about 80% of all resident macrophages in the human body. In the event of liver injury, a variety of substances, including nutrients and gut-derived bacterial products, are brought to the liver via the portal circulation and then excreted by KCs. Several inflammatory cytokines, including tumour necrosis factor-, interleukin-1, interleukin-6, interleukin-12, interleukin-18, and chemokines, are produced by KCs.

10. Lipotoxicity

Hepatic steatosis (lipid buildup in the liver; hepatic steatosis >5% of liver (weight)) is caused by a combination of endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress, oxidative stress, and activation of Kupffer (KCs), which in turn induces inflammatory cytokines and inflammation. Lipotoxicity also reduces mitochondrial activity and disrupts the electron transport chain (ETC), both of which result in increased reactive oxygen species

(ROS) generation. NASH is made worse by a cycle in which reactive oxygen species (ROS) destroy the mitochondria. Hepatic stellate cells (HSCs) are triggered into action by inflammation and reactive oxygen species (ROS), resulting in an overabundance of extracellular matrix and the development of fibrosis.

10.1 Fatty acid uptake

Over half of the FAs in NAFLD come from blood circulation, as was indicated previously. Triglyceride lipase, monoglyceride lipase, and hormone-sensitive lipase all play roles in the release of FAs from adipose tissue. With obesity and NAFLD, insulin resistance increases lipolysis in adipose tissue, leading to a higher release of free fatty acids (FAs) into the bloodstream. The liver absorbs FAs from the bloodstream via passive diffusion and active transport. In the liver, fatty acid uptake is facilitated by the fatty acid translocase CD36, the fatty acid transport proteins (FATPs), and the fatty acid binding proteins (FABPs). CD36 has been found to have a significant correlation with the development of NAFLD. The expression of CD36 is increased in both animal models of NAFLD and persons with the disease. Mice lacking CD36 have FA uptake rates similar to controls. Yet, increased expression of CD36 improves FA absorption in the liver, suggesting a role for the protein in pathological conditions. Individuals who are extremely overweight tend to have greater levels of the liver marker CD36 in both mRNA and protein.

11. Triglyceride synthesis

The glycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferase (GPAT) is the bottleneck enzyme in the de novo process of TG production. The glycerol-3-phosphate (G3P) pathway is responsible for the production of over 90% of TGs. Pages 5–32 of the 2022 issue of *Biomolecules* Lysophosphatidic acid (LPA) is produced by GPAT from glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate (G3P) and long-chain acyl-CoA. Endoplasmic

reticulum acylglycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferases (AGPAT) convert LPA to phosphatidic acid (PA). Diacylglycerol is produced when phosphatidic acid (PA) is dephosphorylated by phosphoinositide phosphatase (PIP2, Lipin) (DG). The DG acyltransferase is responsible for catalysing the conversion of DG to TG (DGAT). Evidence that TGs have a protective impact on the liver comes from a study in which inhibiting DGAT2 in obese mice improved hepatic steatosis while exacerbating liver damage and fibrosis.

11.1 Lipoprotein secretion

Monolayers of phospho-lipids, free cholesterol, and apolipoproteins surround the lipid core (TG and cholesteryl esters) of lipoproteins. Very low density lipoproteins (VLDL) are TG-rich lipoproteins secreted by the liver to deliver fatty acids (FAs) to peripheral organs like adipose tissue, muscle, and the heart. The long form of apoprotein B (apoB100) is expressed in the liver of mammals, while the short form (apoB48) is expressed in the intestine and the liver of rodents. Apobec1, an mRNA editing enzyme, modifies the full apoB mRNA in the colon and liver of rodents by replacing the cytidine at position 6666 with uracil, hence creating a premature stop codon. A protein termed apoB48 is produced from this apoB mRNA that has been truncated such that it only contains the first 48 amino acids of the full-length apoB protein. Two key proteins, apolipoprotein B and mitochondrial transfer protein, are involved in both steps of VLDL assembly (MTTP).

12. Treatment of NAFLD

As of yet, there is no one treatment for NAFLD that has been shown to be 100 percent successful. Improve steatosis and slow the disease's progression are the primary therapy objectives. The cornerstones of disease management are radical adjustments to one's way of life and the treatment of underlying causes. Adjuvant therapies, such as medical and surgical procedures, are used when initial treatment has failed.

12.1 Lifestyle interventions

Multiple studies have demonstrated that the liver's function and histology can improve with sustained weight loss brought on by calorie restriction and increased physical activity. 64,65 The biochemical and histological characteristics of NAFLD have been found to improve with both exercise and nutrition treatments alone or in combination. Several studies have shown that a diet low in carbohydrates and high in fat is effective in lowering

metabolic syndrome and NAFLD risk factors.

12.2 Insulin sensitizing agents

Pathophysiological pathways of NAFLD are hypothesised to be modified by insulin sensitising drugs due to the disease's association with IR and metabolic syndrome. The antidiabetic pharmaceutical metformin, along with the thiazolidinedione class of drugs, have received the most research attention.

12.2 Metformin

The histological markers, including steatosis, inflammation, hepatocellular ballooning, and fibrosis, did not improve with metformin usage despite considerable improvements in IR and hepatic transaminases (AST and ALT).

12.2 Thiazolidinediones

These medications enhance glucose homeostasis by regulating insulin sensitivity in tissues via PPAR-g signalling. In this class of medications, rosiglitazone and pioglitazone have received the most attention for treating type 2 diabetes. Pioglitazone has replaced rosiglitazone as the preferred treatment for diabetes, because of the dangers of cardiovascular disease and other adverse effects associated with the latter.

12.3 Antioxidants

Since oxidative stress is so crucial to the development of NAFLD, several researchers have looked into how antioxidants might help. 71–74 In this group, vitamin E has received the most attention from researchers. Histological markers, including steatosis, hepatocyte ballooning, lobular inflammation, and fibrosis, all showed considerable improvement after supplementation.

12.4 Incretin-based therapy

NAFLD treatment studies have focused primarily on dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors and GLP-1 analogues (including exenatide, liraglutide, lixisenatide, dulaglutide, and semaglutide) (e.g., sitagliptin, saxagliptin, vildagliptin, alogliptin and linagliptin). Both groups of medications are particularly helpful in the management of T2DM because they increase insulin production from the pancreas in response to meals and have additional effects on other organs.

12.5 Lipid lowering agents

Treatment with lipid-lowering medications is helpful, especially for patients who also suffer from NAFLD and dyslipidaemia. Statin therapy may result in decreased serum aminotransferase levels and resolution of

ultrasonological anomalies, according to a 2013 Cochrane review; however, the studies included in the study were small and carried a significant risk of bias.

12.6 Drugs for weight loss

The pathogenic pathways of NAFLD may be affected by weight-loss medications, making them beneficial for some individuals. Most of these drugs have just a moderate effect on weight loss, and others have been pulled off sale because of harmful side effects.

12.7 Orlistat

By blocking fat absorption in the digestive tract, this drug aids in the management of obesity. In two randomised controlled trials (RCTs), orlistat was found to have a positive effect on patients with nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), although it was unclear whether this was due to the weight loss that the drug induced or to some other direct effect.

12.8 Lorcaserin

This appetite suppressor, when used in conjunction with healthy lifestyle modifications, can lead to a loss of roughly four percent of body weight in a year. Data from three randomised controlled trials (RCTs) of lorcaserin in individuals with NAFLD demonstrated a small but statistically significant improvement in cardiovascular outcomes and a decrease in ALT levels compared to placebo (Table 2).

12.9 Naltrexone/bupropion combination

About 5% of excess weight loss can be attributed to this medication combination. Patients who dropped more than 10% of their body weight in a year with the higher dose of the combination had detectable decreases in hepatic aminotransferase levels.

12.10 Phentermine/topiramate

It has been shown that this combination helps people lose weight and may help them reverse NAFLD.

12.11 Liraglutide

In order to treat obesity in individuals who do not have diabetes, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency have just approved high-dose liraglutide therapy (3 mg daily).

12.12 Selonsertib

Akt1-Inhibitor: A Protein that Blocks Apoptosis
Inhibition of the serine/threonine kinase apoptotic signal-regulating kinase 1 (ASK1) reduced inflammation and fibrosis in animal models of nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH).

12.13 Bariatric surgery

A recent meta-analysis found that both histology and biochemical indicators of NAFLD improved significantly in patients who had undergone bariatric surgery for their obesity. Liver enzyme levels, including alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, and gamma-glutamyl transferase, and histological features of the disease, such as steatosis, fibrosis, hepatocyte ballooning, and lobular inflammation, improved in surgical patients.

12.13 Vitamin E

Vitamin E, a powerful antioxidant, has been studied for its potential as a treatment for non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD). Vitamin E reduces oxidative stress in animal models of NASH by downregulating iNOS and nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase, and it enhances lipid and glucose metabolism via activating the Nrf2/CES1 signalling pathway

Table 2 FDA Approval Drug Rational

Drug	Rationale
Metformin	December 29, 1994
Thiazolidinediones	1990
Locaserin	2012
Orlistat	1999
Phenetermine	1959
Victoza (Liraglutide)	January 25 ,2010

13. Conclusion

The global epidemic of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease is mostly attributable to the accumulation of triglycerides and free fatty acids in the liver, a condition exacerbated by obesity and insulin resistance (NAFLD). If liver steatosis progresses to fibrosis, however, it can have devastating effects. Many variables have been proposed as contributors to the onset of NAFLD, including metabolic disturbances or insulin resistance at the disease's physiological centre. In addition, in the not-too-distant future, high-quality and strong genetic analysis will be within the financial reach of clinicians, giving them access to a lot of information and the opportunity for superior targeted treatment. The same is true for progress in diagnostic imaging and biochemical testing. Currently, there are a number of drugs and supplements that may be utilised in the treatment of NAFLD; however, none of

them have proven to be the "magic bullet" in stopping this alarming trend. Lifestyle factors, including a healthy diet and regular exercise, are crucial in preventing nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD).

Conflict of Interest

Author(s) declared no conflict of interest.

Ethical Compliance Standard

NA.

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References

[1] Cotter TG, Rinella M. Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Disease 2020: The State of the Disease. *Gastroenterology*. 2020;158(7):1851-1864.

[2] Younossi ZM, Blissett D, Blissett R, Henry L, Stepanova M, Younossi Y, Racila A, Hunt S, Beckerman R. The economic and clinical burden of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease in the United States and Europe. *Hepatology*. 2016.

[3] Gill MG, Majumdar A. Metabolic associated fatty liver disease: Addressing a new era in liver transplantation. *World J Hepatol*. 2020;12(12):1168-118.

[4] Singh S, Osna NA, Kharbanda KK. Treatment options for alcoholic and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: A review. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2017;23(36):6549-6570.

[5] Benedict M, Zhang X. Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: An expanded review. *World J Hepatol*. 2017;9(16):715-732.

[6] Teng YX, Xie S, Guo PP, Deng ZJ, Zhang ZY, Gao W, Zhang WG, Zhong JH. Hepatocellular Carcinoma in Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease: Current Progresses and Challenges. *J Clin Transl Hepatol*. 2022;10(5):955-964.

[7] VanWagner LB, Rinella ME. Extrahepatic Manifestations of Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Disease. *Curr Hepatol Rep*. 2016;15(2):75-85.

[8] Fabbrini E, Sullivan S, Klein S. Obesity and nonalcoholic fatty liver disease: biochemical, metabolic, and clinical implications. *Hepatology*. 2010;51(2):679-89.

[9] Heyens LJM, Busschots D, Koek GH, Robaey G, Francque S. Liver Fibrosis in Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease: From Liver Biopsy to Non-invasive Biomarkers in Diagnosis and Treatment. *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 2021;8:615978.

[10] Williams R, Periasamy M. Genetic and Environmental Factors Contributing to Visceral Adiposity in Asian Populations. *Endocrinol Metab (Seoul)*. 2020;35(4):681-695.

[11] Albhaisi S, Chowdhury A, Sanyal AJ. Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease in lean individuals. *JHEP Rep*. 2019;1(4):329-341

[12] Agbim U, Carr RM, Pickett-Blakely O, Dagogo-Jack S. Ethnic Disparities in Adiposity: Focus on Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease, Visceral, and Generalized Obesity. *Curr Obes Rep*. 2019;8(3):243-254.

[13] Shakir AK, Suneja U, Short KR, Palle S. Overview of Pediatric Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Disease: A Guide for General Practitioners. *J Okla State Med Assoc*. 2018;111(8):806-811.

[14] Fitzpatrick E, Dhawan A. Noninvasive biomarkers in non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: current status and a glimpse of the future. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2014;20(31):10851-63.

[15] Nassir F. NAFLD: Mechanisms, Treatments, and Biomarkers. *Biomolecules*. 2022;12(6):824.

[16] Lonardo A, Nascimbeni F, Maurantonio M, Marrazzo A, Rinaldi L, Adinolfi LE. Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease: Evolving paradigms. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2017;23(36):6571-6592.

[17] Liu Y, Zhong GC, Tan HY, Hao FB, Hu JJ. Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease and mortality from all causes, cardiovascular disease, and cancer: a meta-analysis. *Sci Rep*. 2019;9(1):11124.